

Data Management

INVENTORY OF PROJECTS

The nccr – on the move produces a wide range of deliverables, most of which can be accessed during and after the project duration through the links provided in this document.

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The electronic version of this document contains hyperlinks to relevant websites.

Status : June 29th, 2026

Find the latest version here:
www.nccr-onthemove.ch/DataManagement/Inventory.pdf
Zenodo.org: 10.5281/zenodo.20395605

Visualizations:
<https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/nccr.on.the.move>

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Data Management Plans

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DMP status: [Accepted](#) [Accepted with comments](#) [Revision required](#)

Datasets

Phase I	Click to access	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
Vital Statistics IP1 INVENTORY / Philippe Wanner	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683899
Migration Mobility Survey 2016 IP1 INVENTORY / Philippe Wanner	FORS	10.23662/FORS-DS-854-1
Mapping Demographics IP2 IMPACT / Philippe Wanner	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683351
Survey of Recrutement Practices in the Hotel Sector in Switzerland IP7 LM-POLICY / Flavia Fossati	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683517
Labor Market Effects IP9 LM-EFFECTS / Tobias Müller	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683613
Datasets Linking Swiss Scholar Information System and Migrant Data IP12 INTEL-STUDENTS / Annique Lombard	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683704
Outsourcing Asylum Reception IP13 EXCLUSION / Camilla Alberti	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.5059885
Immigration Detention in Switzerland (2011-2017) IP13 EXCLUSION / Christin Achermann	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683841
Skills On the Move IP17 FAMILIES / Flavia Cangià	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.4926080
Families in Geographical Itinerary IP17 FAMILIES / Tania Zittoun	Contractual	10.5281/zenodo.18683761
Ethnic Discrimination in the Swiss Labour Market IP18 DISCRIMINATION / Robin Stunzi	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6675500
Outgroup Prejudice and Perceptions IP20 ATTITUDES / Islam Borinca	OSF	osf.io/hwmsc/

Phase II	Click to access	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
Support and Opposition to Migration II IP22 HISTORY / Didier Ruedin	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.4327120
Multilevel strategies of political inclusion II IP22 HISTORY / Lorenzo Piccoli	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6793311
MiTSopro Visualization II IP22 HISTORY / Andreas Perret	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.5006449
Immigration Trends Using Google Data II IP23 DATA / Philippe Wanner	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.5046620
Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018-2020-2022 II IP23 DATA / Philippe Wanner	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7756022
Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018-2020 II IP23 DATA / Philippe Wanner	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.4651223
Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018 II IP23 DATA / Philippe Wanner	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.4147324
Replication data for: The quiet politics of migration supranationalization – Commission entrepreneurship and the intra-Corporate Transferee Directive II IP24 MLG-TRADE / Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik	Zenodo	10.1080/07036337.2023.2295374
Immigrant-origin candidates in Switzerland II IP24 MLG-TRADE / Anna-Lena Nadler	Dataverse	10.7910/DVN/066P80
Migration Provisions in Trade Agreements II IP24 MLG-TRADE / Philipp Lutz	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7837954
Refugee Resettlement in OECD countries II IP24 MLG-TRADE / Philipp Lutz	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.5762158
Individual Attitudes Towards Migration II IP25 TRADE-GENDER / Tobias Müller	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.5036337
Local-to-local electoral connections for migrants II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/6GRNJ
Replication Code for: Politicising Immigration in Times of Crisis II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Didier Ruedin	OSF	osf.io/wcvqm/
Structural Racism in Switzerland II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/KM4PE
The Extent of Résumé Whitening II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/K3P6G
Directory of migration research institutions II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Lorenzo Piccoli	EUI	10.17605/OSF.IO/UKWDR
Resilience at School 2019-2021 II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Wassilis Kassis	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7515139

Resilience at School II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Wassilis Kassis	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.4982490
How one gesture curbed ethnic discrimination II IP26 INEQUAL-RESILIENCE / Didier Ruedin	OSF		10.17605/OSF.IO/RU8Y6
Attitudes Towards the Distribution of Covid-19 Vaccines II IP27 WELFARE / Carlo Knotz	FORS	C	10.23662/FORS-DS-1264-1
Replication Data for: Who deserves student finance? II IP27 WELFARE / Mia Gandenberge	OSF		10.17605/OSF.IO/7QSN2
Political attitudes in Switzerland during COVID-19 II IP27 WELFARE / Mia Gandenberger	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.4471366
Replication Data for: Integration as a Precondition for Enfranchisement? Swiss Public Opinion on Noncitizen Voting Rights II IP27 WELFARE / Alyssa M. Taylor	OSF		10.17605/OSF.IO/R7KD8
Dataset to: All of the same type? II IP27 WELFARE / Angie Gago	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.7605100
A recast framework for welfare deservingness perceptions II IP27 WELFARE / Carlo Knotz	OSF	C	10.17605/OSF.IO/37ME5
Comparative Study on Hiring Discrimination II IP27 WELFARE / Flavia Fossati	Contractual	C	10.5281/zenodo.18683954
Survey Experiment on Hiring Preferences in Three Countries II IP27 WELFARE / Flavia Fossati	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.4312838
Survey Experiment on Employer Apprenticeship Preferences II IP27 WELFARE / Flavia Fossati	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.4309133
Replication Data for: What Drives Opposition to Social Rights for Immigrants? Clarifying the Role of Psychological Predispositions II IP27 WELFARE / Carlo Knotz	OSF		10.17605/OSF.IO/KDRP7
Struggles for democracy: strategies and resources II IP28 URB-CITIZENSHIP / Katrin Sontag	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.7573628
Governing Migration and Social Cohesion through Integration Requirements II IP29 INTEGRATION / Christin Achermann	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.8090642
Women leaving the playpen - Replication package II IP30 NATURALIZATION / Michaela Slotwinski	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.7064906
Power Sharing at the Local Level II IP30 NATURALIZATION / Alois Stutzer	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.4915919
Learning from Null Effects: A Bottom-Up Approach II IP30 NATURALIZATION / Dominik Hangartner	Dataverse		10.7910/DVN/PEGIUB

Non-citizen Voting Rights II IP30 NATURALIZATION / Dominic Hangartner	Contractual	C
The Social Network of Solidarity With Migrants II IP31 NORMS / Antoine Robelin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/F4UXG
Replication Data for: Valence of immigration news, perceived threat, and support for restrictive immigration policy: A multilevel study across 26 countries II IP31 NORMS / Matthieu Vétois	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/PB8RW
Replication Data for: Immigrant political participation is associated with more positive majority immigration attitudes across European countries and Swiss cantons II IP31 NORMS / Judit Kende	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/SPZY7
Replication material EUP article II IP31 NORMS / Xavier Fernández-i-Marín	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/AYCWT
From Perceived Polarization to Collective Action II IP31 NORMS / Eva Green	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/8K95N
Dataset to: Willingness to engage in intergroup contact with refugees II IP31 NORMS / Juan Manuel Falomir-Pichastor	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/X6MWQ
Meta-Humanization II IP31 NORMS / Islam Borinca	OSF	osf.io/58gbr
Ingroup Norms II IP31 NORMS / Islam Borinca	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/WJH26
Mobile EU Citizens II IP31 NORMS / Xavier Fernández-i-Marín	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/MD8TW
The Power of Intergroup Apology II IP31 NORMS / Juan Manuel Falomir-Pichastor	OSF	osf.io/g8pa4/
Services for Swiss Abroad II IP31 NORMS / Lorenzo Piccoli	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.5047376
Link between immigrant presence and anti-immigrant prejudice II IP31 NORMS / Judit Kende	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/J5H4E
The role of minority discrimination in two cross-national studies II IP31 NORMS / Judit Kende	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/KVBW9
Sedative effects of intergroup contact II IP31 NORMS / Emanuele Politi	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/CNGFE
Location Decision II IP31 NORMS / Salomon Bennour	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.6965553
Stress during COVID-19 Lockdown II IP31 NORMS / Matthieu Vétois	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/TBC4V
Migrant Entrepreneurs as Agents of Development II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Yvonne Riaño	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7542604

Replication materials for the article: Weaving transnational spaces: Peruvian and Colombian suitcase traders moving across South American borders II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Yvonne Riaño	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.14003689
A Review of Transnational Migrant Entrepreneurship II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Laure Sandoz	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.6603112
Cross-border Migrant Entrepreneurship in Switzerland II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Christina Mittmasser	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.5771957
Informal Practices in Transnational Entrepreneurship II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Laure Sandoz	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.4911350
Entrepreneurship as Self-Improvement II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Laure Sandoz	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.10521961
A Valuable Resource for Border-Crossing Entrepreneurs II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Yvonne Riaño	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.7542675
Entrepreneurs de la migration II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Laure Sandoz	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.6602998
Worker Cooperatives' Potential for Migrant Women's Self-Empowerment II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Yvonne Riaño	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.5070764
Understanding Brain Waste II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Yvonne Riaño	Zenodo		10.1002/psp.2456
Highly Skilled Migrant II IP32 ENTREPRENEURSHIP / Yvonne Riaño	Zenodo		10.3390/admsci11010005
Transnational Ageing Survey 2020-2021 II IP33 AGEING / Laura Ravazzini	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.7049814
Older adults on the move II IP33 AGEING / Livia Tomás	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.8261134
Transnational Ageing Survey 2020 II IP33 AGEING / Mihaela Nedelcu	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.5775519
On the move while remaining still II IP34 TRANSNATIONALITIES / Oliver Pedersen	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.6594603
Lost in transition to adulthood II IP34 TRANSNATIONALITIES / Louis Vuilleumier	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.6640844
(Im)moral mobilities in a Swiss Borderland II IP34 TRANSNATIONALITIES / Emmanuel Charmillot	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.6759220
Stereotypes Explaining Discrimination II IP35 DIFFUSION / Lea Portmann	Dataverse		10.7910/DVN/BNSXB2
Penalized Due to Ingroup Favoritism or Outgroup Hostility II IP35 DIFFUSION / Lea Portmann	Dataverse		10.7910/DVN/VXRL7A
Replication Data for: Electoral Discrimination II IP35 DIFFUSION / Daniel Auer	Dataverse		10.7910/DVN/EIINMP

Safe Country Policies II IP35 DIFFUSION / Frowin Rausis	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.5886863
Responsiveness of Local Politicians to Immigrants II IP36 BORDERS / Didier Ruedin	OSF		10.17605/OSF.IO/UDSYN
Travel Restrictions II IP36 BORDERS / Lorenzo Piccoli	EUI	C	hdl.handle.net/1814/68359
Pandemic Border Discourses II IP36 BORDERS / Marie-Eve Belanger	Zenodo		10.5281/zenodo.6619705
Mobility and Border Control II IP36 BORDERS / Lorenzo Piccoli	EUI	C	hdl.handle.net/1814/68358
From 'digital nomadism' to 'rooted digitalism' II IP38 IMMOBILITY / Flavia Cangià	Zenodo	C	10.5281/zenodo.10069594

Phase III	Click to access	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
Replication Data for: Do immigrants at bay keep the xenophobes away? III IP39 GLOBAL GOVERNANCE / Philipp Lutz	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.18394989
Shared nationality in social exchange III IP40 NARRATIVES / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/GPTX7
Replication Data for: Narratives of Crisis and Their Influence on Attitudes, Behaviour, and Policies of Migration and Mobility: A Framework III IP40 NARRATIVES / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/2KN9B
Replication Data for: Experimental evidence on how implicit racial bias affects risk preferences III IP40 NARRATIVES / Daniel Auer	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/ACYQS
Replication Data for: Towards a precise and reflexive use of migration-related terminology in quantitative research: Criticism and Suggestions III IP40 NARRATIVES / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/4T7NQG
Replication materials for the article: How Do People Perceive Immigrants? III IP40 NARRATIVES / Carlo Knotz	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/JP7U5
Replication Data for: Migration debates in the political party arena during the Covid-19 pandemic in Austria III IP40 NARRATIVES / Didier Ruedin	OSF	osf.io/gc6eq/
Replication Data for: Resisting Societal Bordering through Political Subjectivity III IP40 NARRATIVES / Anna Marino	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.17985668
Replication Data for: Framing Migration and Migrants Through Border Crises III IP40 NARRATIVES / Anna Marino	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.17986388
Replication Data for: Narrating Crises of Europe's Southernmost Borderscapes III IP40 NARRATIVES / Anna Marino	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.18230472
Replication Data for: A tale of two cities III IP40 NARRATIVES / Anna Marino	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.17986127
Replication Data for: When politicians feel pressure to represent: Evidence from South Africa III IP40 NARRATIVES / Didier Ruedin	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/SMZXG
Replication Data for: Re-evaluating the welfare preferences of radical-right voters III IP40 NARRATIVES / Mia Gandenberger	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/NUPAZ
Replication Data for: Distrusting them and creating us III IP40 NARRATIVES / Anna Marino	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.17989246
European Commission Dataset III IP41 EMIGRATION / Udochi Great Uchechukwu	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.14290522

Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018-2020-2022-2024 III IP42 LONGITUDINAL / Philippe Wanner	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.15358475
Replication data for: Welfare Chauvinism among Voters and Political Parties: Exploring Preferences for Restricting EU Migrants' Access to Social Assistance in Switzerland III IP43 ATTITUDES / Mia Gandenberger	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/2CEQU
Replication Data for: Migrantization of mobile EU citizens III IP43 ATTITUDES / Anita Manatschal	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/CWT42
Replication Data for: Who is willing to help Ukrainian refugees and why? Individual prosocial dispositions and superordinate European identity related to intergroup helping intentions III IP43 ATTITUDES / Jessica Gale	OSF	osf.io/xkrbn/
Replication materials for the article: Welfare solidarity in multi-ethnic societies: can social investment reduce the anti-immigrant bias? III IP43 ATTITUDES / Mia Gandenberger	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/USPNQ
Replication materials for the article: Social and institutional inclusion in multi-ethnic schools enable better intergroup relations for majority youth and higher school achievement for minority youth III IP43 ATTITUDES / Judit Kende	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/3ZW24
Replication data for: Macro-Level Climate and Minority Voice: How Indigenous Multiculturalism Relates to Collective Action III IP43 ATTITUDES / Jessica Gale	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/6YBVW
Replication data for: Immigration salience and double standards: Differential impacts on prejudice and far-right support between Ukrainian refugees and other immigrant groups III IP43 ATTITUDES / Matthieu Vétois	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/KSA6E
Replication data for: Normalizing far-right nativist policies: How source–message dissociation and negative immigration news reduce emotional discomfort and increase policy support III IP43 ATTITUDES / Matthieu Vétois	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/VWNM7
Replication data for: Are immigrants allowed to criticize the government? Ingroup identity, economic threat, and majority group support for immigrant civil liberties in the US, Switzerland, and Turkey III IP43 ATTITUDES / Mia Gandenberger	OSF	10.17605/OSF.IO/R7TZ5
Replication Data for: The Free Movement of People and the Success of Far-Right Parties: Evidence from Switzerland's Border Liberalization III IP44 HIRING-DECISIONS / Ala Alrababah	Dataverse	10.7910/DVN/X9STDF
Federal Administrative Court Case law III IP48 LEGACIES / Mathis Schnell	Zenodo	C 10.5281/zenodo.15861764

Sexual Asylum

III IP48 LEGACIES / Mathis Schnell

Zenodo

10.5281/zenodo.15861942

Replication Data for: Integration as a totalizing institution

III IP48 LEGACIES / Stefan Manser-Egli

Zenodo

10.5281/zenodo.17531285

Visualizations

	Click to access	Short URL
Publications	Publications	https://tabsoft.co/3vVogcP
Datasets	Datasets	https://tabsoft.co/3zCisXO
Network Phase III	Network III	https://tabsoft.co/3SbWVvQ

Phase I

Migrant's Arrivals in Municipalities	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/37kSzA8
Departure Rates over Time	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3kSs48d
Status Changes over Time	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yfJHAd
Naturalization Rates over Time	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3vND0ua
Naturalization Rates by Municipality	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3P517MI
Asylum Seekers in Switzerland	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3KK8hT6
Migration-Mobility Survey 2016	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3KOnen1
Administrative Motive of Entry	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/38Xi372
International Flows with Switzerland	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3kOH72O
Migrant's Educational Level	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3wsZSP1
Residence of Swiss Living Abroad	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3klzET4
Emigration and Return of Swiss Citizen	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yonBCj
Migrant's and the Labor Market	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yjORli
Foreign Born Population in Europe	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yeYmCt
Employment Rate of Immigrants	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3sh9Phb
Cantonal Portraits	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3FpzYEM
Acquisition of Citizenship in Europe	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/382BAmN
Legal Indicators	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yjqCDN
Citizenship and Voting Rights	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3ygnCUB
Attitudes on Migration Issues in Europe	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/387BsSI
Correspondence Testing	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3KOnen1

Phase II

Support and Opposition to Migration	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3906ps0
MiTSopro	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yhAoX4
Migration-Mobility Survey 2018-2020	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3LQiJKg
City Growth	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3KMx0WR
Evolution of Income	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3kJYu50
School Study	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3KPVQFo
Anti-immigrant prejudice	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3wbsZWQ
Fair Share of Refugees	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3yjsrAD
Maps by Migrants	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3P4E44H
Aeging Survey	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3wt8IMH
Safe Country Policies	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3906hJ2
Directory of Migration Research Institutions	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3LR15pL
Covid-19 Outbreak	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3MVBWKB
Mobility and Borders	Tableau	https://tabsoft.co/3Fkrrhm

Phase III

Demands to the UNHCR	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/532yue5ms
Timeline	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/48vddwmm
Crisis Model	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/564u3dnr
Lexicographic Analysis in Migration Rhetorics	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/2k89ycpm
Migration Flows in the Pacific Region	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/5dhy9rf9
Refugee Organizations	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/hu3thksf
Mobility Patterns	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/fu4bdp27
Demographic Balance	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/y95mxe5m
Specific Nationalities	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/5n96vkt
Asylum Employment	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/285h4wy6
Federal Asylum Centers	Tableau	https://tinyurl.com/55xsf3n2

Phase I

Projects descriptions,
registrations at FORS inventory,
available Codebooks
and publication list

Hypertext links in this section:

Click on the grey project
name to see its
publications

Click on the black project title to visit its nccr - on the move homepag

Click on the blue sub-project title to view its description on a repository

Click on colored squares to access a specific dataset on a repository

Z ZENODO **O** OSF **D** Dataverse **F** FORS **E** EUI CADMUS

Click on a black square to visit the provider of a confidential dataset **P**

Click to download a standard Codebook **C**

Click to visit an interactive Visualization **V**

Phase I

IP1 INVENTORY

Inventory of Individual Statistical Data on Migration to, from and within Switzerland in a Post-Census World

Philippe Wanner (University of Geneva) and Rosita Fibbi (University of
Neuchâtel)

[Migration-Mobility Survey. Survey on living as a migrant in Switzerland](#)

F **C** Migration Mobility Survey 2016

[Interrelations between Family and Migration Trajectories](#)

C **C** Vital Statistics

[Mobilité spatiale et intégration résidentielle dans le parcours de vie.
L'influence du statut migratoire.](#)

[Exploring international and internal forms of multiple migrations:
Evidence from Switzerland 1998-2013](#)

T	Migration-Mobility Survey 2016	https://tabsoft.co/3KOnen1
T	Migrant's and the Labor Market	https://tabsoft.co/3yjORli
T	Emigration and Return of Swiss Citizen	https://tabsoft.co/3yonBCj
T	Residence of Swiss Living Abroad	https://tabsoft.co/3klzET4
T	Migrant's Educational Level	https://tabsoft.co/3wsZSP1
T	International Flows with Switzerland	https://tabsoft.co/3kOH72O
T	Administrtrive Motive of Entry	https://tabsoft.co/38Xi372
T	Migrant's Arrivals in Municipalities	https://tabsoft.co/37kSzA8
T	Naturalization Rates by Municipality	https://tabsoft.co/3P517MI
T	Asylum Seekers in Switzerland	https://tabsoft.co/3KK8hT6
T	Status Changes over Time	https://tabsoft.co/3yfJHad
T	Naturalization Rates over Time	https://tabsoft.co/3vND0ua
T	Departure Rates over Time	https://tabsoft.co/3kSs48d

IP2 IMPACT

Mapping the Demographics of the New Forms of Mobility and Measuring Their Socioeconomic Impact

Philippe Wanner (University of Geneva)

[Skill Composition and Occupational Incorporation of Early and Recent Immigrants in Switzerland: The Case of](#)

[Female Employment after Childbirth: Differences between Native and Immigrant Women in Switzerland](#)

[Employment Trajectories of Recent Immigrants in Switzerland](#)

[Modeling Future Migration Trends and their Impact on the Swiss Pension System](#)

C C Mapping Demographics

[Segregation patterns among foreigners in Switzerland: a multi-scalar approach \(1990-2014\)](#)

IP3 LEGAL-REGIME

From “Traditional” to “New” Migration: Challenges to the International Legal Migration Regime

Alberto Achermann (University of Bern) and Jörg Künzli (University of Bern)

[From “Traditional” to “New” Migration: Challenges to the International Legal Migration Regime](#)

[The Right to Citizenship in International Human Rights Law](#)

[Civil Status Recognition in the European Union](#)

[Schengen Visa Policy. The Human Rights Perspective](#)

IP4 UNDOCUMENTED

New Wine in Old Skins? Containing “New” Migration with the Traditional Framework – The Example of Sans-Papiers in Switzerland

Martina Caroni (University of Lucerne)

[Determining the Best Interests of the Child: The Case of Sans-Papiers Children in Switzerland](#)

IP5-11 LAW-ECONOMICS

The Law and Economics of Migration Policy

Alberto Achermann (University of Bern)

[Legal Pluralism and Efficiency in International Marriage Law](#)

IP6 EUROPEAN LAW

The Emergence of a European Law on Foreigners

Sarah Progin-Theuerkauf (University of Fribourg)

[The emergence of a European Law on Foreigners](#)

IP7 LM-POLICY

Integration through Active Labor Market Policies

Giuliano Bonoli (IDHEAP Lausanne)

[Integration through Active Labor Market Policies](#)

C C [Survey of Recruitment Practices in the Hotel Sector in Switzerland](#)

IP8 HIGHLY-SKILLED

The Mobility of the Highly Skilled towards Switzerland

Walter Leimgruber (University of Basel)

[The Mobility of the Highly Skilled Towards Switzerland](#)

[Comparative Case Study on the Situation of Refugees at Universities in France, Germany, and Switzerland](#)

[Civic engagement of recent migrants in Switzerland](#)

[Intermediaries, Channels and Privileges: A Journey into the Mobility of the 'Highly Skilled' towards Switzerland](#)

IP9 LM-EFFECTS

Labor Market Effects and the Political Economy of “New” Migration to Switzerland

Tobias Müller (University of Geneva)

[Attitudes towards Immigrants in Switzerland](#)

C **C** Labor Market Effects

[Labor Market Effects and the Political Economy of ‘New’ Migration to Switzerland](#)

IP10 ECONOMIC-IMPACT

The Economic Impact of New Migration and Integration Issues

Alois Stutzer (University of Basel)

[Attitudes towards immigrants, foreigners' location choices and support of the welfare state](#)

[The role of non-citizen voting rights in migrants' integration](#)

IP12 INTEL-STUDENTS

International Student Mobility between the South and the North

Etienne Piguet (University of Neuchâtel)

[International Students in Switzerland. Trajectories, Stay Rates and Intentions of Post-Graduation Mobility](#)

C **C** Datasets Linking Swiss Scholar Information System and Migrant Data

[New directions in policies of international student migration: Switzerland in global comparative perspective](#)

IP13 EXCLUSION

Restricting Immigration: Practices, Experiences and Resistance

Christin Achermann (University of Neuchâtel)

[Practices, experiences and perceptions of immigration detention: An ethnography of detention facilities in Switzerland](#)

C **C** Immigration Detention in Switzerland (2011-2017)

[Restricting Immigration: Practices, Experiences and Resistance](#)

Z **C** Outsourcing Asylum Reception

IP14 CITIZENSHIP

Unity and Diversity in Cohesion: Immigration, Citizenship and Federalism

Cesla Amarelle (University of Neuchâtel) and Gianni D'Amato (University of Neuchâtel)

[The Regional Dynamics of Integration and Citizenship Regulation: An International Comparative Perspective](#)

T Foreign Born Population in Europe <https://tabsoft.co/3yeYmCt>

T Acquisition of Citizenship in Europe <https://tabsoft.co/382BAmN>

T Cantonal Portraits <https://tabsoft.co/3FpZyEM>

T Employment Rate of Immigrants <https://tabsoft.co/3sh9Phb>

T Citizenship and Voting Rights <https://tabsoft.co/3ygNCUb>

T Attitudes on Migration Issues in Europe <https://tabsoft.co/387BsSI>

T Legal Indicators <https://tabsoft.co/3yjqCDN>

IP15 PHILOSOPHY

Citizenship and Immigration: An Empirical and Normative Analysis of Swiss Philosophy of Integration

Matteo Gianni (University of Geneva)

[Citizenship and Immigration: An Empirical and Normative Analysis of Swiss Philosophy of Integration](#)

IP16 GENDER

Gender as Boundary Marker in Migration and Mobility: Case Studies from Switzerland

Janine Dahinden (University of Neuchâtel)

[Gender as a Boundary Marker in Migration and Mobility: Case Studies from Switzerland](#)

IP17 FAMILIES

“New Migration” and New Forms of Integration: Families in Geographical Itinerancy

Tania Zittoun (University of Neuchâtel)

[“New Migration” and New Forms of Integration: Families in Geographical Itinerancy](#)

C **C** Families in Geographical Itinerancy

Z **C** Skills On the Move

IP18 DISCRIMINATION

Discrimination as an Obstacle to Social Cohesion

Gianni D’Amato (University of Neuchâtel) and Rosita Fibbi (University of Neuchatel)

[Ethnic discrimination in hiring decisions in the Swiss labour market](#)

Z **C** Ethnic Discrimination in the Swiss Labour Market

T Correspondence Testing <https://tabsoft.co/3KOnen1>

IP19 REGIONS

The Regional Dynamics of Integration and Citizenship Regulation: An International Comparative Perspective

Anita Manatschal (University of Neuchâtel)

IP20 ATTITUDES

The Interplay of Social Norms and Intergroup Contact in Understanding Immigration Attitudes in Multicultural Societies

Eva G. T. Green (University of Lausanne) and Juan Manuel Falomir-Pichastor (University of Lausanne)

[The interplay of social norms and intergroup contact in understanding immigration attitudes in multicultural societies](#)

O Outgroup Prejudice and Perceptions

IP21 REFUGEE-
INTEGRATION

Asylum Policy and Refugee Integration in Norway, Sweden and Switzerland

Dominik Hangartner (University of Zurich)

Phase II

Projects descriptions, publication list and data collection instruments

Hypertext links in this section:

Click on the grey project name to see its publications

Click on the black project title to visit its nccr - on the move homepag

Click on the blue sub-project title to view its description on a repository

Click on colored squares to access a specific dataset on a repository

Z ZENODO **O** OSF **D** Dataverse **F** FORS **E** EUI CADMUS

Click on a black square to visit the provider of a confidential dataset **P**

Click to download a standard Codebook **C**

Click to visit an interactive Visualization **V**

Hub

A Socio-Historical and Demographic Perspective on Migration and Mobility

II IP22 HISTORY

Mobility, Diversity, and the Democratic Welfare State: Contested Solidarity in Historical and Political Comparative Perspective

Gianni D'Amato (University of Neuchâtel) and Jean-Thomas Arrighi (University of Neuchâtel)

Analysis of documents - open *Policy documents*
 Analysis of documents - standardized *Electronic Archives (CH, DE, SE)*

[II_IP22_HISTORY: Mobility, Diversity, and the Democratic Welfare State: Contested Solidarity in Historical and Political](#)

Z **C** MiTSopro Visualization

Politicization of Immigration in the News

Z **C** Multilevel strategies of political inclusion

Z **C** Support and Opposition to Migration

T MiTSopro <https://tabsoft.co/3yhAoX4>

T Support and Opposition to Migration <https://tabsoft.co/3906ps0>

II IP23 DATA

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Explaining and Interpreting Migration Flows and Stocks

Philippe Wanner (University of Geneva)

Secondary analysis - aggregate data *Indicators of Migration*
 Standardized interviews - by e-mail *Migration-Mobility Survey*
 Standardized interviews - by telephone *Migration-Mobility Survey*

Explaining and Interpreting Migration Flows and Stocks in Switzerland

Z C Immigration Trends Using Google Data

Migration-Mobility Survey. Survey on living as a migrant in Switzerland 2016-2018

Z C Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018-2020-2022

Z C Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018-2020

Z C Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018

T Migration-Mobility Survey 2018-2020 <https://tabsoft.co/3LQiJKg>

T City Growth <https://tabsoft.co/3KMx0WR>

T Evolution of Income <https://tabsoft.co/3kJYU50>

II IP36 BORDERS

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The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Bordering Discourses Regarding Migration and Mobility in Europe

Sandra Lavenex (University Geneva)

Analysis of content - standardized *Twitter feeds and press releases*
 Analysis of documents *Twitter feeds and press releases*

The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Bordering Discourses Regarding Migration and Mobility in Europe

E C Travel Restrictions

Z Pandemic Border Discourses

O Responsiveness of Local Politicians to Immigrants

E C Mobility and Border Control

T Mobility and Borders <https://tabsoft.co/3Fkrrhm>

T Covid-19 Outbreak <https://tabsoft.co/3MVBWKB>

T Directory of Migration Research Institutions <https://tabsoft.co/3LR15pL>

Module I

Migration and Social Inequalities

II IP24 MLG-TRADE

Migration Governance through Trade Mobilities

Sandra Lavenex (University of Geneva) and Joachim Blatter (University of Lucerne)

Analysis of documents - standardized	<i>Legislation, court proceedings</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Experts interviews</i>
Secondary analysis - aggregate data	<i>Analysis of quantitative policy datasets</i>

Migration Governance through Trade Mobilities (qualitative)

Migration Governance through Trade Mobilities (mixed-methods)

- Z** Replication data for: The quiet politics of migration supranationalization – Commission entrepreneurship and the intra-Corporate Transferee Directive
- D** Immigrant-origin candidates in Switzerland
- Z C** Refugee Resettlement in OECD countries
- Z C** Migration Provisions in Trade Agreements

II IP25 TRADE-GENDER

Migration and Labor Market Inequality: The Role of Skills, Gender and Trade

Tobias Müller (University of Geneva) and Martina Viarengo (The Graduate Institute, Geneva)

Secondary analysis - aggregate data	<i>Trade data, SSES, Labor Force Survey</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Linked surveys /SSES, Labor Force Survey</i>

Migration and Labor Market Inequality: The Role of Skills, Gender and Trade

- Z** Individual Attitudes Towards Migration
-

Overcoming Inequalities in the Labor Market: Can Educational Measures Strengthen the Agency and Resilience of Migrants, Refugees, and Their Descendants?

Wassilis Kassis (FHNW School of Education) and Didier Ruedin (University of Neuchâtel)

Experiment	<i>Eye-Tracking</i>
	<i>Hiring decisions experiment</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>School-Migrants</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>International household panels</i>
Standardized interviews - by e-mail	<i>School-Migrants</i>

Overcoming Inequalities in the Labor Market: Can Educational Measures Strengthen the Agency and Resilience of Migrants, Refugees, and Their Descendants?

E C Directory of migration research institutions

Z C Resilience at School 2019-2021

Z C Resilience at School

Discrimination in the Housing Market

O The Extent of Résumé Whitening

O Replication Code for: Politicising Immigration in Times of Crisis

O Local-to-local electoral connections for migrants

O How one gesture curbed ethnic discrimination

O Structural Racism in Switzerland

T School Study

<https://tabsoft.co/3KPVQFo>

II IP27 WELFARE

Welfare: Inclusion and Solidarity

Giuliano Bonoli (University of Lausanne), Flavia Fossasti (University of Lausanne) and Francesco Maiani (University of Lausanne)

Analysis of documents - open	<i>Legal texts, policy reports</i>
Experiment	<i>Survey experiment</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Process tracing</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Survey data, not specified</i>

Welfare: Inclusion and Solidarity

- O** **C** A recast framework for welfare deservingness perceptions
- O** Replication Data for: Integration as a Precondition for Enfranchisement? Swiss Public Opinion on Noncitizen Voting Rights
- Z** Dataset to: All of the same type?
- Z** **C** Survey Experiment on Employer Apprenticeship Preferences
- C** **C** Comparative Study on Hiring Discrimination
- Z** **C** Survey Experiment on Hiring Preferences in Three Countries

The IDHEAP/NCCR-on the move survey "Solidarity in times of crisis"

- O** Replication Data for: What Drives Opposition to Social Rights for Immigrants? Clarifying the Role of Psychological Predispositions
- F** **C** Attitudes Towards the Distribution of Covid-19 Vaccines
- O** Replication Data for: Who deserves student finance?
- Z** **C** Political attitudes in Switzerland during COVID-19

Module II

Citizenship and Social Cohesion

II IP28 URB-CITIZENSHIP

Perimeters of Multilayered Democratic Citizenship in a Mobile and Multicultural World

Matteo Gianni (University of Geneva) and Walter Leimgruber (University of Basel)

Analysis of documents - open	<i>Policy analysis</i>
Observation - participant	<i>Anthropological fieldwork</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Policy analysis</i>
Standardized interviews - by e-mail	<i>BE/DE/CH online</i>

Perimeters of Multilayered Democratic Citizenship in a Mobile and Multicultural World

- Z** Struggles for democracy: strategies and resources

II IP29 INTEGRATION

Governing Migration and Social Cohesion through Integration Requirements: A Socio-Legal Study on Civic Stratification in Switzerland

Christin Achermann (University of Neuchâtel) and Stefanie Kurt (HES-SO Valais-Wallis)

Analysis of documents - standardized	<i>Legal texts, internal guidelines</i>
Observation - without participant	<i>Administrations, courts</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Administrations, courts</i>

Governing Migration and Social Cohesion through Integration Requirements: A Socio-Legal Study on Civic Stratification in Switzerland (IP29)

Z **C** Governing Migration and Social Cohesion through Integration Requirements

Governing Migration and Social Cohesion through Integration Requirements: A Socio-Legal Study on Civic Stratification in Switzerland (II_IP29_Integration)

II IP30
NATURALIZATION

Non-Citizen Voting Rights, Naturalization and Integration

Dominik Hangartner (ETH Zurich), Alois Stutzer (University of Basel)

Experiment	<i>Naturalization incentive experiment</i>
Secondary analysis - aggregate data	<i>SFSO, structural data on cantons</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Swiss, Swedish and Danish register data, Illegal behavior accusations (SFSO), Structural survey and linked administrative data (SFSO)</i>
Standardized interviews - by e-mail	<i>Non-citizen voting (2017 data collection)</i>

The Role of Non-Citizen Voting Rights in Migrants' Integration

D Learning from Null Effects: A Bottom-Up Approach

C **C** Non-citizen Voting Rights

Naturalizing Switzerland

Z Women leaving the playpen - Replication package

Z Power Sharing at the Local Level

Societal Norms as Predictors of Behavior and Attitudes regarding Migration among Majorities and Immigrants

Eva G. T. Green (University of Lausanne), Juan Manuel Falomir-Pichastor (University of Geneva), and Anita Manatschal (University of Neuchâtel)

Experiment	<i>Experiment</i>
Secondary analysis - aggregate data	<i>Citizenship and migration policy indices database, official administrative data (e.g. OFS)</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Selects, Migration-Mobility survey, ESS, GMM, register data (STATPOP, relevé structurel)</i>

Societal Norms as Predictors of Behavior and Attitudes regarding Migration among National Majorities and Immigrants

- O Dataset to: Willingness to engage in intergroup contact with refugees
- O From Perceived Polarization to Collective Action
- O The Social Network of Solidarity With Migrants
- O Meta-Humanization
- O Mobile EU Citizens
- O The Power of Intergroup Apology
- Z C Services for Swiss Abroad
- O Replication material EUP article
- O Replication Data for: Immigrant political participation is associated with more positive majority immigration attitudes across European countries and Swiss cantons
- O Replication Data for: Valence of immigration news, perceived threat, and support for restrictive immigration policy: A multilevel study across 26 countries
- O Ingroup Norms
- O Sedative effects of intergroup contact
- Z C Location Decision
- O The role of minority discrimination in two cross-national studies
- O Link between immigrant presence and anti-immigrant prejudice
- O Stress during COVID-19 Lockdown
- T Anti-immigrant prejudice <https://tabsoft.co/3wbsZWQ>

Module III

Transnational Mobilities and
Complex Diversities

II IP32
ENTREPRENEURSHIP

**Migrant Entrepreneurship: Mapping Cross-Border
Mobilities and Exploring the Role of Spatial Mobility
Capital**

Yvonne Riaño (University of Neuchâtel) and Etienne Piguet (University
of Neuchatel)

Observation - participant	<i>Streets, Events, Organizations</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Entrepreneurs, Experts, Gatekeepers</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>SLFS, Migration-Mobility Survey</i>

Border Mobilities and Exploring the Role of Spatial Mobility Capital

Z Worker Cooperatives' Potential for Migrant Women's Self-Empowerment

Z Understanding Brain Waste

Z **C** Entrepreneurs de la migration

Z **C** A Review of Transnational Migrant Entrepreneurship

Z A Valuable Resource for Border-Crossing Entrepreneurs

Z Migrant Entrepreneurs as Agents of Development

Z **C** Entrepreneurship as Self-Improvement

Z Replication materials for the article: Weaving transnational spaces: Peruvian and Colombian suitcase traders moving across South American borders

Z Highly Skilled Migrant

**Migrant Entrepreneurship: Mapping Cross-Border Mobilities and
Exploring the Role of Spatial Mobility Capital**

Z **C** Informal Practices in Transnational Entrepreneurship

Z **C** Cross-border Migrant Entrepreneurship in Switzerland

T Fair Share of Refugees <https://tabsoft.co/3yjsrAD>

T Maps by Migrants <https://tabsoft.co/3P4E44H>

II IP33 AGEING

**Transnational Ageing: Post-Retirement Mobilities,
Transnational Lifestyles and Care Configurations**

Mihaela Nedelcu (University of Neuchâtel) and Eric Crettaz (HES-SO Geneva)

Focus groups	<i>Retirees associations, local actors</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Swiss retirees abroad</i>
Standardized interviews - by e-mail	<i>Survey in Switzerland and abroad</i>

Mobilities, Transnational Lifestyles, and Care Configurations

Z **C** Transnational Ageing Survey 2020

Z **C** Older adults on the move

Z **C** Transnational Ageing Survey 2020-2021

T **A**geing Survey <https://tabsoft.co/3wt8IMH>

II IP34
TRANSNATIONALITIES

**Small Localities at the Outskirts of Europe: Transnational
Mobilities, Diversification and Multi-Scalar Place-Making**

Tania Zittoun (University of Neuchâtel) and Janine Dahinden (University of Neuchâtel)

Analysis of documents - open	<i>Available documents</i>
Observation - without participant	<i>Small localities</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Villagers</i>

**Small Localities at the Outskirts of Europe: Transnational Mobilities,
Diversification, and Multi-Scalar Place-Making**

Z **C** On the move while remaining still

Z **C** Lost in transition to adulthood

Z **C** (Im)moral mobilities in a Swiss Borderland

II IP35 DIFFUSION

The Mobility of Migration Policies: Pathways and Consequences of the Diffusion of Migration Policies

Joachim Blatter (University of Lucerne), Fabrizio Gilardi (University of Zurich)

Analysis of content - open	<i>Parliament attitudes</i>
Analysis of documents - open	<i>Official documents</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Key actors</i>
Secondary analysis - aggregate data	<i>OECD countries</i>

The Mobility of Migration Policies: Pathways and Consequences of the Diffusion of Migration Policies

- D** Penalized Due to Ingroup Favoritism or Outgroup Hostility
- D** Stereotypes Explaining Discrimination
- D** Replication Data for: Electoral Discrimination

Towards transnational voting in/for Europe!?

The Invention of Safe Countries: Mapping the Global Diffusion of an Asylum Policy on the Move

Z C Safe Country Policies

T Safe Country Policies <https://tabsoft.co/3906hJ2>

II IP37 DIGITALIZATION

Digital empowerment: unpacking ICTs-mediated practices of asylum seekers in Turkey and refugees in Switzerland to cope with (im)mobility conditions

Mihaela Nedelcu (University of Neuchâtel)

Analysis of content - standardized	<i>Sub-Saharan African asylum seekers and refugees</i>
Analysis of documents	<i>Sub-Saharan African asylum seekers and refugees</i>
Focus groups	<i>Key observers</i>
Observation - without participant	<i>Sub-Saharan African asylum seekers in Turkey and refugees in Switzerland</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Sub-Saharan African asylum seekers in Turkey and refugees in Switzerland</i>

Digital Empowerment of Asylum Seekers in Turkey and Refugees in Switzerland to Cope With (Im)Mobility Conditions

**The digitalization of work and the (im)mobilities-
boundaries paradox of 'knowledge workers': the end of
highly skilled migration?**

Eric Davoine (University of Fribourg)

Focus groups

*Discussion on scenarios with the
experts*

Qualitative interviews

*HR-experts, IT specialists working
for companies based in Switzerland*

Standardized interviews - by e-mail

Human Resource Experts

**The Digitalization of Work and the (Im)Mobilities/Boundaries Paradox of IT
Specialists**

Z C From 'digital nomadism' to 'rooted digitalism'

Phase III

Projects descriptions, publication list and data collection instruments

Hypertext links in this section:

Click on the grey project name to see its publications

Click on the black project title to visit its nccr - on the move homepag

Click on the blue sub-project title to view its description on a repository

Click on colored squares to access a specific dataset on a repository

Z ZENODO **O** OSF **D** Dataverse **F** FORS **E** EUI CADMUS

Click on a black square to visit the provider of a confidential dataset **P**

Click to download a standard Codebook **C**

Click to visit an interactive Visualization **V**

Module I

Migration-Mobility Narratives

III IP39 GLOBAL GOVERNANCE

The Impact of Crises on the Global Governance of Migration and Mobility: Boost or Blow

Sandra Lavenex (Department of Political Science and International Relations, University of Geneva) and Vincent Chetail (Global Migration Centre, Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies)

Analysis of documents - standardized	<i>Database of central policy documents from international organizations</i>
Experiment	<i>Survey experiment of public opinion on international migration</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Expert interviews, open-structured, with stakeholders involved in international organiza-tions</i>

The Impact of Crises on the Global Governance of Migration: Boost or Blow

Z Replication Data for: Do immigrants at bay keep the xenophobes away?

T Demands to the UNHCR <https://tinyurl.com/532yue5ms>

Narratives of Crisis and Their Influence in Shaping Discourses and Policies of Migration and Mobility

Gianni D'Amato (University of Neuchâtel), Didier Ruedin (University of Neuchâtel) and Matteo Gianni (University of Geneva)

Analysis of content - standardized	<i>Collection of publicly available twitter feeds of politicians</i> <i>Policy documents to expand the Support and Opposition to Migration (SOM) dataset</i>
Analysis of documents	<i>Collection of publicly available twitter feeds of politicians</i> <i>Policy documents to expand the Support and Opposition to Migration (SOM) dataset</i>
Experiment	<i>Survey experiments in Kenya and Nigeria</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Content analysis of party manifest</i> <i>Correlate the media analysis with data from the MMS</i>

Narratives of Crisis and Their Influence

- O Replication materials for the article: How Do People Perceive Immigrants?
- O Replication Data for: Narratives of Crisis and Their Influence on Attitudes, Behaviour, and Policies of Migration and Mobility: A Framework
- O Replication Data for: Experimental evidence on how implicit racial bias affects risk preferences
- O Replication Data for: Towards a precise and reflexive use of migration-related terminology in quantitative research: Criticism and Suggestions
- O Replication Data for: Migration debates in the political party arena during the Covid-19 pandemic in Austria
- O Replication Data for: When politicians feel pressure to represent: Evidence from South Africa
- O Shared nationality in social exchange
- Z C Replication Data for: Resisting Societal Bordering through Political Subjectivity
- Z C Replication Data for: Framing Migration and Migrants Through Border Crises
- Z C Replication Data for: Distrusting them and creating us
- Z C Replication Data for: A tale of two cities
- O Replication Data for: Re-evaluating the welfare preferences of radical-right voters
- Z C Replication Data for: Narrating Crises of Europe's Southernmost Borderscapes
- T **Timeline** <https://tinyurl.com/48vddwm>
- T **Crisis Model** <https://tinyurl.com/564u3dnr>
- T **Lexicographic Analysis in Migration Rhetorics** <https://tinyurl.com/2k89ycpm>
- T **Migration Flows in the Pacific Region** <https://tinyurl.com/5dhy9rf9>

III IP41 EMIGRATION

A European Desert? The Territorial Economics and Politics of Emigration in Crisis Regions

Olivier Crevoisier (Institute of Sociology, University of Neuchâtel), Jean-Thomas Arrighi (Institute of History, University of Neuchâtel), Sean Mueller (Institute of Political Studies, University of Lausanne)

Analysis of content - standardized	<i>Collection of regional laws, guidelines and/or decrees that set out how the regional governments sees, reacts to, intends to plan or foresees personal mobility</i>
Analysis of documents	<i>Collection of regional laws, guidelines and/or decrees that set out how the regional governments sees, reacts to, intends to plan or foresees personal mobility</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Expert and stakeholder interviews</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Secondary analysis of economic and demographic data from public statistical agencies</i>

A European Desert? The Territorial Economics and Politics of Emigration in Crisis Regions

Z **C** European Commission Dataset

T Refugee Organizations <https://tinyurl.com/hu3thksf>

Module II

Socio-Economic Inequality in Times of Crises

III IP42 LONGITUDINAL

The Longitudinal Impact of Crises on Economic, Social, and Mobility-Related Outcomes: The Role of Gender, Skills, and Migration Status

Tobias Müller (University of Geneva), Martina Viarengo (The Graduate Institute, Geneva) and Philippe Wanner (University of Geneva)

Secondary analysis	<i>Extension of longitudinal nccr – on the move dataset</i>
Standardized interviews - by e-mail	<i>Continuation of the nccr – on the move Migration Mobility Survey</i>

The Longitudinal Impact of Crises on Economic, Social, and Mobility-Related Outcomes: The Role of Gender, Skills, and Migration Status

Z **C** Migration Mobility Survey 2016-2018-2020-2022-2024

T Mobility Patterns <https://tinyurl.com/fu4bdp27>

III IP43 ATTITUDES

Attitudes Towards Migration and Democracy in Times of Intertwined Crises

Eva G. T. Green (University of Lausanne), Anita Manatschal (University of Neuchâtel), Juan M. Falomir Pichastor (University of Geneva).

Experiment	<i>Survey experiments and/or correlational surveys in Ukraine, South Africa, Switzerland, Chile; subsequent analyses of NCCR CH/US/TUR Democracy survey experiments</i>
Secondary analysis - individual data	<i>Afrobarometer, ISSP, Chilean Longitudinal Study of Intercultural Relations (ELRI), New Zealand Attitudes and Values Survey (NZAVS), Living Together in Switzerland (ZidS), Citizens' Attitudes Under Covid-19 panel (CAUCP)</i>

Attitudes Towards Migration and Democracy in Times of Intertwined Crises

- O** Replication materials for the article: Welfare solidarity in multi-ethnic societies: can social investment reduce the anti-immigrant bias?
- O** Replication Data for: Who is willing to help Ukrainian refugees and why? Individual prosocial dispositions and superordinate European identity related to intergroup helping intentions
- O** Replication data for: Are immigrants allowed to criticize the government? Ingroup identity, economic threat, and majority group support for immigrant civil liberties in the US, Switzerland, and Turkey
- O** Replication data for: Welfare Chauvinism among Voters and Political Parties: Exploring Preferences for Restricting EU Migrants' Access to Social Assistance in Switzerland
- O** Replication data for: Normalizing far-right nativist policies: How source–message dissociation and negative immigration news reduce emotional discomfort and increase policy support
- O** Replication data for: Immigration salience and double standards: Differential impacts on prejudice and far-right support between Ukrainian refugees and other immigrant groups
- O** Replication data for: Macro-Level Climate and Minority Voice: How Indigenous Multiculturalism Relates to Collective Action
- O** Replication materials for the article: Social and institutional inclusion in multi-ethnic schools enable better intergroup relations for majority youth and higher school achievement for minority youth
- O** Replication Data for: Migrantization of mobile EU citizens
- T** Specific Nationalities <https://tinyurl.com/5n96vkut>
- T** Demographic Balance <https://tinyurl.com/y95mxe5m>
- T** Asylum Employment <https://tinyurl.com/285h4wy6>

III IP44 HIRING-
DECISIONS

**Monitoring Ethnic and Immigrant Discrimination in Hiring
Decisions in Times of Crisis**

**Dominik Hangartner (Immigration Policy Lab, ETH Zurich), Michael
Siegenthaler (KOF Konjunkturforschungsstelle, ETH Zurich)**

Secondary analysis - aggregate data *Secondary analyses of MMS and
other longitudinal NCCR datasets*

Secondary analysis - individual data *Statistical analyses of employment
website Job-Room*

**Monitoring Ethnic and Immigrant Discrimination in Hiring Decisions in
Times of Crisis**

D **Replication Data for: The Free Movement of People and the
Success of Far-Right Parties: Evidence from Switzerland's
Border Liberalization**

Module III

Regimes of (Im)Mobility

III IP45 AGENCY

**Dealing with Crises in Liminal Spaces: The Agency of
Ukrainian and Syrian Forced Migrants in Three National
Contexts**

**Walter Leimgruber (University of Basel), Mihaela Nedelcu (University of
Neuchâtel)**

Analysis of content - standardized *Follow activists activities across
different digital platforms*

Analysis of documents *Follow activists activities across
different digital platforms*

Analysis of documents - open *Descriptions, Webpage texts, Flyer,
publications by activists, refugees
and other local actors that are
publicly available*

Qualitative interviews *Fieldnotes taken in liminal spaces,
at meetings of initiatives and after
informal con-versations with
refugees and activists*

**Dealing with Crises in Liminal Spaces: The Agency of Ukrainian and
Syrian Forced Migrants in Three National Contexts**

III IP46 DATA POLITICS **Data Politics and New Regimes of Mobility and Control During and After the COVID-19 Pandemic**

Ola Söderström (University of Neuchâtel), Sophie Oldfield (University of Basel & University of Cape Town)

Analysis of documents - open	<i>Policy documents on mobility tracing.</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with different target groups: govern-ment officials, members of digital platform corporations and civil society organisa-tions</i>

Data Politics and New Regimes of Mobility and Control During and After the COVID-19 Pandemic

III IP47 IMAGINATION **Societal Crises and Personal Sense-Making: Transitions, Mobility, and Imagination Across the Lifecourse**

Nathalie Muller Mirza (University of Geneva), Tania Zittoun (University of Neuchâtel) International partner: Alex Gillespie (London School of Economics and Political Science)

Analysis of content - standardized	<i>Sample of longitudinal online diaries</i>
Analysis of documents	<i>Sample of longitudinal online diaries</i>
Observation	<i>Observations in diarists' lived environment</i>
Standardized interviews	<i>Interviews with diarists</i>

Societal Crises and Personal Sense-Making: Transitions, Mobility, and Imagination Across the Lifecourse

III IP48 LEGACIES **Towards a Novel Mobility Regime? The Legacies of the COVID-19 Pandemic Regarding the Governance of Human Movement**

Christin Achermann (LAPS and CDM, University of Neuchâtel), Janine Dahinden (LAPS, University of Neuchâtel), Francisco Klauser (IGG, University of Neuchâtel)

Analysis of documents - open	<i>Textual analysis of literature, reports, institutional guidelines</i>
Qualitative interviews	<i>Interviews with the key persons of the respective institutions</i>

Towards a Novel Mobility Regime? The Legacies of the COVID19 Pandemic Regarding the Governance of Human Movement

Z Replication Data for: Integration as a totalizing institution

Z C Sexual Asylum

Z C Federal Administrative Court Case law

T Federal Asylum Centers <https://tinyurl.com/55xsf3n2>

Evolving (Im)mobility Regimes: Migrant Workers' Entitlement and Precarization in Times of Crisis

Eric Crettaz (HES-SO Geneva, School of Social Work), Stefanie Kurt (HES-SO Valais-Wallis, School of Social Work), Francesco Maiani (University of Lausanne), Eva Mey (ZHAW Social Work)

Qualitative interviews

In-depth interviews with migrant workers

Secondary analysis - individual data

Analyses based on comparative European datasets that are widely used in social sciences. In particular, Eurostat's Survey on Income and Living Conditions and Labour Force Survey

Evolving (Im)Mobility Regimes: Migrant Workers' Entitlement and Precarization in Times of Crisis

NCCR III

NCCR, Activity unrelated to a specific IP

Gianni D'Amato

[nccr – on the move](#)

Publications

Phase I

IP1_INVENTORY

Publications Phase I (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Cattacin, Sandro, Rosita Fibbi and Philippe Wanner. "La nouvelle seconde génération. Introduction au numéro spécial". *Swiss Journal of Sociology*, 42, 2: 209–217, 2016. Collaborative (IP18 and IP1).
<https://doi.org/10.1515/sjs-2016-0009>

Lacroix, Julie and Elena Vidal Coso. "Differences in Labor Supply by Birthplace and Family Composition in Switzerland: the Role of Human Capital and Household Income". *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 20, 3: 659-684, 2018. Collaborative (IP2 and IP1).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-018-0623-8>

Lacroix, Julie and Jonathan Zufferey. "A Life Course Approach to Immigrants' Relocation: Linking Long- and Short-distance Mobility Sequences". *Migration Letters*, 16, 2: 283–300, 2019. Collaborative (IP2 and IP1).
<https://doi.org/10.33182/ml.v16i2.683>

Lacroix, Julie, Alain Gagnon and Philippe Wanner. "Family changes and residential mobility among immigrant and native-born populations: Evidence from Swiss administrative data". *Demographic Research*, 43, 41: 1199-1234, 2020. Collaborative (IP23 and IP1).
<https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2020.43.41>

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Working Paper

Loretan, Alicia and Philippe Wanner. "The determinants of naturalization in Switzerland between 2010 and 2012". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 13, 2017.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4433965>

Steiner, Ilka and Philippe Wanner. "Towards a new data set for the analysis of migration and integration in Switzerland". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 1, 2015.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4434189>

Replication data available on Contractual <https://zenodo.org/records/18683351>

Replication data unavailable (National statistics data, under contract)

Research Reports

Ruedin, Didier, Daniel Auer, Julie Lacroix and Eva Zschirnt. "Ethnische Diskriminierung auf dem Schweizer Wohnungsmarkt". : 21, 2019. Collaborative (IP26, IP18, IP7 and IP1).
<https://www.bwo.admin.ch/bwo/de/home/Wohnungsmarkt/studien-und-publikationen/diskriminierung-auf-der-schweizer-wohnungsmarkt.html>

Thesis

Lacroix, Julie. "Interrelations entre trajectoires résidentielles, familiales et professionnelles: Le parcours de vie des immigrés en Suisse". *Geneva, Switzerland: Université de Genève*, 2019
<https://archive-ouverte.unige.ch/unige:125594>

IP2_IMPACT

Publications Phase I (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Lacroix, Julie and Elena Vidal Coso. "Differences in Labor Supply by Birthplace and Family Composition in Switzerland: the Role of Human Capital and Household Income". *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 20, 3: 659-684, 2018. Collaborative (IP2 and IP1).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-018-0623-8>

Lacroix, Julie and Jonathan Zufferey. "A Life Course Approach to Immigrants' Relocation: Linking Long- and Short-distance Mobility Sequences". *Migration Letters*, 16, 2: 283–300, 2019. Collaborative (IP2 and IP1).

<https://doi.org/10.33182/ml.v16i2.683>

Milivinti, Alice and Giacomo Benini. "A Bayesian Semiparametric Approach for Trend-Seasonal Interaction: an Application to Migration Forecasts". *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society A.*, 182, 3: 805-830, 2019.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/rssa.12436>

Milivinti, Alice. "A spatio-temporal analysis of migration". *Empirical Economics*, 57, 4: 1411-1442, 2019.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-018-1514-8>

Vidal Coso, Elena and Enrique Ortega-Rivera. "Skill Composition and Occupational Incorporation of Early and Recent Immigrants in Switzerland: the case of Italians and Spaniards". *International Migration*, 55, S1: 86-111, 2017.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/imig.12320>

Vidal Coso, Elena. "Female employment following childbirth: differences between native and immigrant women in Switzerland". *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 45, 9: 1667-1692, 2019.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2018.1444983>

Wanner, Philippe, Jonathan Zufferey and Juliette Fioretta. "The Impact of Migratory Flows on the Swiss Labour Market. A Comparison Between In- and Outflow". *Migration Letters*, 13, 3: 411-426, 2016.

<https://doi.org/10.33182/ml.v13i3.293>

Wanner, Philippe. "Inégalités spatiales de mortalité en Suisse. Le rôle de la migration internationale sur l'espérance de vie de la population des métropoles". *Espace populations sociétés*, 2018, 1-2: 24, 2018.

<https://doi.org/10.4000/eps.7555>

Replication data available on Contractual <https://zenodo.org/records/18683899>

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Zufferey, Jonathan and Michel Oris. "Inégalités spatiales de mortalité en Suisse : l'influence des contextes sur les différentiels entre natifs et migrants". *Espace populations sociétés*, 2018, 1-2: 23, 2018.

<https://doi.org/10.4000/eps.7576>

Zufferey, Jonathan, Ilka Steiner and Didier Ruedin. "The Many Forms of Multiple Migrations: Evidence from a Sequence Analysis in Switzerland, 1998 to 2008". *International Migration Review*, 55, 1: 254-279, 2021.

Collaborative (IP23, IP26 and IP2).

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0197918320914239>

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Book Chapters

Vidal Coso, Elena and Enrique Ortega-Rivera. "From "Old" to "New" Southern European Migrants in Switzerland". In *Actas del VIII Congreso sobre Migraciones Internacionales en España*, S33/63–S33/90. Granada: Instituto de Migraciones, 2015

<https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=6200835>

Vidal Coso, Elena. "Employment Trajectories of Recent Immigrants in Switzerland". In *Migrants and Expats: The Swiss Migration and Mobility Nexus*, edited by Wanner, Philippe and Ilka Steiner, 123-159. Cham: Springer, 2019

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05671-1_6

Zufferey, Jonathan. "Who Are the Serial Movers? Sociodemographic Profiles and Reasons to Migrate to Switzerland Among Multiple International Migrants". In *Migrants and Expats: The Swiss Migration and Mobility Nexus*, edited by Wanner, Philippe and Ilka Steiner, 83-100. Cham: Springer, 2019

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05671-1_4

Working Paper

Lombard, Annique and Jonathan Zufferey. "International Graduates in Switzerland: Transitioning into the Labor Market". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 21, 2019. Collaborative (IP12 and IP2).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4432342>

Milivinti, Alice. "How many Migrants does the Swiss Pension System Need?". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 19, 2018.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4432356>

Zufferey, Jonathan. "Segregation Patterns among Foreigners in Switzerland: A Multi-Scalar Approach (1990 – 2014)". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 22, 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4432332>

Thesis

Milivinti, Alice. "Modeling Future Migration Trends and their Impact on the Swiss Pension System". *Geneva, Switzerland: University of Geneva*, 2018
<https://doi.org/10.13097/archive-ouverte/unige:111744>

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Journal Articles

Zufferey, Jonathan. "Investigating the migrant mortality advantage at the intersections of social stratification in Switzerland: The role of vulnerability". *Demographic Research*, 34: 899–926, 2016.
<https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2016.34.32>

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Fidalgo, Antonio, Marco Pecoraro, Alberto Holly and Philippe Wanner. "A nonparametric analysis of the healthy immigrant effect". *IRENE Working Papers. Institut de recherches économiques – Université de Neuchâtel*, WP-16-15, 2016. Collaborative (IP18 and IP2).
<https://ideas.repec.org/p/irn/wpaper/16-15.html>

Rellstab, Sara, Marco Pecoraro, Alberto Holly, Philippe Wanner and Karine Renard. "The migrant health gap and the role of labour market status: Evidence from Switzerland". *IRENE Working Papers. Institut de recherches économiques – Université de Neuchâtel*, WP-16-14, 2016.
<https://ideas.repec.org/p/irn/wpaper/16-14.html>

IP3_LEGAL-REGIME

Publications Phase I (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Achermann, Alberto and Stefan Schlegel. "Jusletter Special Issue Migrationsrecht". *Jusletter*, 14.03.2016, 2016.
<http://jusletter.weblaw.ch/juslissues/2016/839.html>

de Groot, David A.J.G.. "Free Movement of Dual EU Citizens". *European Papers*, 3, 3: 1075-1113, 2018.
<http://www.europeanpapers.eu/en/e-journal/free-movement-of-dual-eu-citizens>

de Groot, David A.J.G.. "HvJ EU 02-06-2016, C-438/14, EHRC 2016/202". *European Human Rights Cases*, 202, 2016.
<https://www.recht.nl/vakliteratuur/europa/aflevering/25341/european-human-rights-cases/2016/10/?delete=1#a408640>

de Groot, David A.J.G.. "Law by blood or blood by law?". *RSC Working Papers, RSCAS 2015/80*: 30-31, 2015.
<http://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/37578>

Hanke, Philip C., Marek Wieruszewski and Marion Panizzon. "The 'spirit of the Schengen rules', the humanitarian visa, and contested asylum governance in Europe – The Swiss case". *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 45, 8: 1361-1376, 2019. Collaborative (IP5-11 and IP3).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2018.1441615>

von Rütte, Barbara. "Das Neue Bürgerrechtsgesetz". *Schweizerische Anwaltsrevue*, 05/17: 202-214, 2017.
<https://anwaltsrevue.recht.ch/fr/epaper/13986/detail#202>

von Rütte, Barbara. "Die erleichterte Einbürgerung für Jugendliche der dritten Generation". *Jusletter*, 20.03.2017, 2017.
<https://jusletter.weblaw.ch/fr/juslissues/2017/885/die-erleichterte-ein-44b3d331bc.html> ONCE#section178ed2e9-4aae-4ee8-9b67-e77c587830d3

von Rütte, Barbara. "Social Identity and the Right to Belong – The ECtHR's Judgment in Hoti v. Croatia". *Tillburg Law Review*, 24, 2: 147-155, 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.5334/tilr.150>

Wieruszewski, Marek. "Schengen visas for refugees: Switzerland's practice". *Europejski Przegląd Sądowy*, 2016, 7: 31-35, 2016.
<https://www.profinfo.pl/sklep/europejski-przeglad-sadowy,7252,r.2016.nr.7.html#5>

Book

Panizzon, Marion, Gottfried Zürcher and Elisa Fornalé. "The Palgrave Handbook of International Labour Migration. Law and Policy Perspectives". *Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2015*
<http://www.palgrave.com/de/book/9781137352200#aboutBook>

von Rütte, Barbara. "The Human Right to Citizenship: Situating the Right to Citizenship within International and Regional Human Rights Law". *Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill Nijhoff, 2022*
<https://brill.com/display/title/62482>

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Book Chapters

Achermann, Alberto and Barbara von Rütte. "Kommentierung der Artikel 37 und 38 der Schweizerischen Bundesverfassung (Bürgerrecht, Erwerb und Verlust des Bürgerrechts)". In *"Schweizerische Bundesverfassung (BV), Basler Kommentar"*, edited by Waldmann, Bernhard, Eva Maria Belser and Astrid Epiney, 771-792. *Basel: Helbing Lichtenhahn Verlag, 2015*
<https://www.helbing.ch/detail/ISBN-9783719033187/Bundesverfassung-BV>

Achermann, Alberto and Martin Hemmi. "Internationale Entwicklungen mit Bedeutung für die Schweiz". In *"Jahrbuch für Migrationsrecht 2016/2017 - Annuaire du droit de la migration 2016/2017"*, edited by Achermann, Alberto, Cesla Amarelle, Martina Caroni, Astrid Epiney, Jörg Künzli and Peter Uebersax, 535-577. *Bern: Stämpfli Verlag, 2017*

<https://www.staempfliverlag.com/detail/ISBN-9783727227738/Jahrbuch-f%FCr-Migrationsrecht-20162017---Annuaire-du-droit-de-la-migration-20162017>

de Groot, David A.J.G.. "Law by Blood or Blood by Law?". In *"Debating Transformations of National Citizenship"*, edited by Bauböck, Rainer, 127-130. *Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018*
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92719-0_25

de Groot, Gerard-René and David A.J.G. de Groot. "Civil status and the freedom of movement in the EU". In *"Privatrecht, Wirtschaftsrecht, Verfassungsrecht: Privatinitiative und Gemeinwohlorizonte in der europäischen Integration"*, edited by Stumpf, Cordula, Friedemann Kainer and Christian Baldus, 1420-1426. *Baden-Baden: Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft mbH & Co.*
<https://doi.org/10.5771/9783845264783-1420>

Panizzon, Marion, Gottfried Zürcher and Elisa Fornalé. "Introduction: Conceptualizing a Pluralist Framework for Labour Migration". In *"Palgrave Handbook on International Labor Migration. Law and Policy Perspectives"*, edited by Panizzon, Marion, Gottfried Zürcher and Elisa Fornalé, 1-14. *Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2015*
https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137352217_1

Panizzon, Marion. "Art. 100 LETr". In *"Code annoté de droit des migrations, Volume II: Loi sur les étrangers (LETr)"*, edited by Amarelle, Cesla and Nguyen Minh Son, 1077-1118. *Bern: Stämpfli, 2017*
<https://www.staempfliverlag.com/detail/ISBN-97837272288753/Code-annot%E9-de-droit-des-migrations>

Panizzon, Marion. "Kranke Migranten als verletzte Menschen: Wann schützt Völkerrecht vor Ausschaffung?". In *"Flüchten – ankommen – teilhaben."*, 129-153. *Zurich: Seismo, 2017*
<https://www.seismoverlag.ch/fr/daten/fluchten-ankommen-teilhaben/>

Panizzon, Marion. "Trade and migration linkages in EU external migration policies: Relief, root-cause reduction or rights protection?". In *"Pathways towards Legal Migration into the EU: Reappraising concepts, trajectories and policies"*, edited by Carrera, Sergio, Andrew Geddes, Elspeth Guild and Marco Stefan, 128-141. *Brussels: Center for European Public Policy (CEPS), 2017*
<https://www.ceps.eu/publications/pathways-towards-legal-migration-eu-reappraising-concepts-trajectories-and-policies>

Vitiello, Daniela and Marion Panizzon. "Political Economy and International Migration Law". In *"The Political Economy of International Law: A European Perspective"*, edited by Fabbricotti, Alberta, 409-436. *Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd, 2016*
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781785364402.00028>

von Rütte, Barbara. "Rechtsentwicklungen in der Schweiz". In *"Jahrbuch für Migrationsrecht 2016/2017 - Annuaire du droit de la migration 2016/2017"*, edited by Achermann, Alberto, Cesla Amarelle, Martina Caroni, Astrid Epiney, Jörg Künzli and Peter Uebersax, 371-409. *Bern: Stämpfli Verlag, 2017*
<https://www.staempfliverlag.com/detail/ISBN-9783727227738/Jahrbuch-f%FCr-Migrationsrecht-20162017---Annuaire-du-droit-de-la-migration-20162017>

Working Paper

de Groot, David A.J.G.. "Pending Case C-438/14 Nabil Peter Bogendorff von Wolffersdorff – Or is it Peter Mark Emanuel Graf von Wolffersdorff Freiherr von Bogendorff?". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series, 5, 2016*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4434161>

Research Reports

Guild, Elspeth, Isobel Roele, Marion Panizzon, Thomas Gammeltoft-Hansen and Violeta Moreno Lax. "What is a Compact? Migrants' Rights and State Responsibilities Regarding the Design of the UN Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration". : 35, 2017.

https://rwi.lu.se/app/uploads/2017/10/RWI_What-is-a-compact-test_101017-senaste-1.pdf

Thesis

de Groot, David A.J.G.. "The many faces of civil status recognition - A legal analysis in the light of EU citizenship and the case law of the European Court of Justice and the European Court of Human Rights". *Bern, Switzerland: University of Bern, 2021*

https://swisscovery.sls.ch/permalink/41SLSP_NETWORK/1ufb5t2/alma991170743610905501

von Rütte, Barbara. "The Human Right to Citizenship - From State Privilege to Individual Right". *Bern, Switzerland: University of Bern, 2020*

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Publications Phase I (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

von Rütte, Barbara and Stefan Schlegel. "Auf dem falschen Fuss entlastet. Die Auswirkungen der geplanten BGG-Revision auf das Migrationsrecht". *Jusletter, 14.03.2016, 2016.*

https://jusletter.weblaw.ch/juslissues/2016/839/auf-dem-falschen-fus_7c54c8bc37.html_ONCE

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Book

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<https://www.staempfliverlag.com/detail/ISBN-9783727259623/Jahrbuch-f%FCr-Migrationsrecht-20152016---Annuaire-du-droit-de-la-migration-20152016>

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<https://www.staempfliverlag.com/detail/ISBN-9783727227738/Jahrbuch-f%FCr-Migrationsrecht-20162017---Annuaire-du-droit-de-la-migration-20162017>

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Book Chapters

Achermann, Alberto and Cesla Amarelle. "Kommentierung: Art. 53, 54 und 58 LEtr". In *"Code annoté de droit des migrations, Volume II: Loi sur les étrangers (LEtr)", edited by Amarelle, Cesla, Minh Son Nguyen and Minh Son Nguyen. Bern: Stämpfli, 2017* Collaborative (IP14 and IP3).

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IP7_LM-POLICY

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IP8_HIGHLY-SKILLED

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IP9_LM-EFFECTS

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IP10_ECONOMIC-IMPACT

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Publications Phase I (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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IP12_INTEL-STUDENTS

Publications Phase I (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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IP18_DISCRIMINATION

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IP19_REGIONS

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Phase II

II_IP22_HISTORY

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II_IP23_DATA

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Journal Articles

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Research Reports

Piccoli, Lorenzo, Leslie Ader, Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, Christina Mittmasser, Oliver Pedersen, Aurélie Pont, Frowin Rausis and Petra Sidler. "Mobility and border control in response to the COVID-19 outbreak dataset". : 14, 2020. Collaborative (IP22, IP35, IP34, IP32, IP31, IP26, IP24 and IP23).

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II_IP24_MLG-TRADE

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Publications Phase II (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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II_IP25_TRADE-GENDER

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II_IP26_INEQUAL-RESILIENCE

Publications Phase II (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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II_IP28_URB-CITIZENSHIP

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II_IP29_INTEGRATION

Publications Phase II (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

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II_IP30_NATURALIZATION

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II_IP32_ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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II_IP35_DIFFUSION

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Journal Articles

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II_IP36_BORDERS

Publications Phase II (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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II_IP37_DIGITALIZATION

Publications Phase II (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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II_IP38_IMMOBILITY

Publications Phase II (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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Replication data unavailable (No SNSF data collection funding)

Phase III

III_IP39_GLOBAL-GOVERNANCE

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Alvarado, Mariana, Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, Sandra Lavenex and Philipp Lutz. "Business migration between labour and trade: evidence from Switzerland". *Comparative Migration Studies*, 13, 1: 60, 2025. Collaborative (IP24 and IP39).
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Lavenex, Sandra and Frowin Rausis. "Chessboard politics: the contested emergence of EU return and readmission norms". *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*: 1-21, 2026.
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Lavenex, Sandra and Karin Vaagland. "Discursive and behavioural sources of regime erosion: the case of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)". *Journal of European Public Policy*: 1-26, 2025.
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Lavenex, Sandra, Philipp Lutz and Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik. "Migration governance through trade agreements: insights from the MITA dataset". *The Review of International Organizations*, 19: 147-173, 2024.
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Publications Phase III (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

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III_IP40_NARRATIVES

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Auer, Daniel and Didier Ruedin. "Experimental evidence on how implicit racial bias affects risk preferences".

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Chueri, Juliana, Mia K. Gandenberger, Alyssa M. Taylor, Carlo M. Knotz and Flavia Fossati. "Re-evaluating the welfare preferences of radical-right voters: evidence from a vignette experiment". *West European Politics*, 48, 7: 1681-1709, 2025. Collaborative (IP40, IP43 and IP27).

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Genoni, Andreas and Didier Ruedin. "When expectations backfire: educational differences in declining destination attachment among recent immigrants". *Social Forces*, 104, 4: 1519–1538, 2026.

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Knotz, Carlo M., Juliana Chueri and Alyssa M. Taylor. "Populist right-wing voting: the (conditional) role of implicit bias". *Acta Politica*, 61: 199-218, 2026. Collaborative (IP40 and IP27).

<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41269-024-00369-z>

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Marino, Anna and Matteo Gianni. "Resisting Societal Bordering through Political Subjectivity: Aboubakar Soumahoro's Activism in Italy. Narratives and Counter-narratives on Migrants' Political Subjectivity in Contemporary Italy". *Current Issues in Migration Research*, 2, 2: 66-74, 2025.

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Replication data available on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/17985668>

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Marino, Anna and Sara De Athouguia Filipe. "Distrusting 'them' and creating 'us': migration and the uses of the past by populist radical right parties in southern Europe". *Frontiers in Political Science*, Volume 7, 2025. Collaborative (IP40 and IP41).

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III_IP41_EMIGRATION

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III_IP42_LONGITUDINAL

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Journal Articles

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III_IP43_ATTITUDES

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III_IP44_HIRING-DECISIONS

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Alrababah, Ala, Andreas Beerli, Dominik Hangartner and Dalston Ward. "The Free Movement of People and the Success of Far-Right Parties: Evidence from Switzerland's Border Liberalization". *American Political Science Review*, 119, 3: 1426–1445, 2025.

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III_IP45_AGENCY

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Journal Articles

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Working Paper

Hategekimana, Vestin, Anna Marino, Maeva Perrin, Eloise Thompson, Jessica Gale, Mia Gandenberger, Simon Noori, Didier Ruedin, Aldina Camenisch, Lucas Oesch and Robin Stünzi. "Crises, Migration and (Im) Mobility: Towards a Reflexive and Multilevel Approach". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 37: 33, 2024. Collaborative (IP48, IP47, IP45, IP43, IP42 and IP40).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832029>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Research Reports

Kaymak, Ayşe, Cansu Akbaş Demirel, Cesla Amarelle, Doğa Elçin, Esin Küçük, Ibrahim Soysüren, Kemal Vural Tarlan, Lina Megahead, Neva Ö. Öztürk, Omar Kadkoy and Orçun Ulusoy. "Temporary Protection Regime. Recent Developments, Challenges, and Perspectives for the Future". : 73, 2025.

https://gocarastirmalaridernegi.org/wp-content/uploads/Temporary-Protection-Regime_EN_2_compressed.pdf

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Publications Phase III (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Saraçoğlu, Cenk. "Beyond the freedom of movement: rethinking the global migration regime through the right to homeland". *Globalizations: 1-22*, 2026.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2026.2662803>

Replication data unavailable (N/A)

III_IP46_DATA-POLITICS

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Aegerter, Jonas and Ola Söderström. "Digital platforms as contact zones: urban reshaping and colonial aesthetics in Palermo". *Digital Geography and Society*, 9, 100127, 2025.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666378325000169>

Replication data unavailable (No SNSF data collection funding)

Barella, Jennifer. "Geodata and territorial governance: the institutional trajectory of the Système d'Information du Territoire Genevois (SITG)". *Netcom*, 39, 3/4: 1-29, 2026.

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Greyling, Saskia and Corey R. Johnson. "Materialising Digital Borderscapes: Examining the Effects of Digital Systems on Asylum Seekers and Refugees". *Social Inclusion*, 14, 10871: 130-148, 2025.

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Törnberg, Petter and Ola Söderström. "Comparative platform urbanism: Cities in a world of platforms". *Digital Geography and Society*, 8, 100119, 2025.

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Törnberg, Petter, Ola Söderström, Jennifer Barella, Saskia Greyling and Sophie Oldfield. "Artificial intelligence and the state: Seeing like an artificial neural network". *Big Data & Society*, 12, 2, 2025.

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Törnberg, Petter. "How platforms govern: Social regulation in digital capitalism". *Big Data & Society*, 10, 1: 1-13, 2023.

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Book

Söderström, Ola and Ayona Datta. "Data Power in Action. Urban Data Politics in Times of Crisis". *Bristol, UK: Bristol University Press*, 2023

<https://doi.org/10.51952/9781529233551>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

III_IP47_IMAGINATION

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Bernal Marcos, Marcos José, Tania Zittoun and Alex Gillespie. "Beyond narratives of decline versus success: retirement through the lens of a diary". *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 40: 76, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-025-00973-3>

Clifford Pedersen, Oliver. "Maintaining the future through recurrent crises". *Culture & Psychology*, 31, 1: 96-115, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1354067X231204298>

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Gillespie, Alex and Tania Zittoun. "Ruptures as Imagined and Theorized: Symbolic Resources for Dealing With the Unexpected". *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 59, 4: 91, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12124-025-09966-9>

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Muller Mirza, Nathalie. "Learning and Crises in Human Development. A Sociocultural and Dialogical Approach". *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 59, 4: 92, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12124-025-09940-5>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Pedersen, Oliver Clifford, Maeva Perrin and Tania Zittoun. "Resonating Crises: A Longitudinal Study of Ruptures in Times of Crises". *Human Arenas*, 2025.

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Perrin, Maeva and Oliver Clifford Pedersen. "In Search of Manifestations and Imaginations of the Climate Crisis: A Longitudinal Analysis of an Online Diary". *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 59, 4: 65, 2025.

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Piccoli, Lorenzo, Matteo Gianni, Didier Ruedin, Christin Achermann, Janine Dahinden, Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, Mihaela Nedelcu and Tania Zittoun. "What Is the Nexus between Migration and Mobility? A Framework to Understand the Interplay between Different Ideal Types of Human Movement". *Sociology*, 58, 5: 1019-1037, 2024. Collaborative (IP40, IP48, IP47 and IP45).

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<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12124-025-09946-z>

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Zittoun, Tania, Oliver Clifford Pedersen, Alex Gillespie, Nathalie Muller Mirza and Maeva Perrin. "Crisis and Human Development". *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 59, 4: 94, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12124-025-09947-y>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Zittoun, Tania. "Integrative Perspectives on Human Development: Dynamic and Semiotic". *Integrative Psychological and Behavioral Science*, 57, 4: 1150-1157, 2023.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12124-023-09783-y>

Replication data unavailable (Other secondary data)

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Gillespie, Alex, Vlad Glăveanu and Constance de Saint Laurent. "Pragmatism and Methodology: Doing Research That Matters with Mixed Methods". *Cambridge: Cambridge University Press*, 2024

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/265842335AF5B7D87FEB6D978C04085F>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

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Muller Mirza, Nathalie and Valérie Tartas. "Learning in dialogues through aesthetic experiences. Some theoretical and methodological issues". In *"Re-theorising Learning and Research Methods in Learning Research"*, edited by Damsa, Crina, Antti Rajala, Giuseppe Ritella and Jasperina Brouwer, 16. London: Routledge, 2023

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Zittoun, Tania and Alex Gillespie. "A Sociocultural Approach to Identity through Diary Studies". In *"Cambridge Handbook of Identity"*, edited by Bamberg, Michael, Carolin Demuth and Meike Watzlawik, 345-365. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022

<https://vbn.aau.dk/en/publications/cambridge-handbook-of-identity-under-contract>

Replication data unavailable (In process)

Zittoun, Tania, Martina Cabra, Oliver Clifford Pedersen and Hana Hawlina. "Thinking the lifecourse through single cases". In *"Ten Years of Idiographic Science"*, edited by Salvatore, Sergio and Jaan Valsiner, 205-2018. Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing, 2023

<https://www.infoagepub.com/products/Ten-Years-of-Idiographic-Science>

Replication data unavailable (Other secondary data)

Zittoun, Tania. "Affects in integrative developmental psychologies". In *"Conflict and Change: Integrating Social and Developmental Psychology"*, edited by Psaltis, Charis and Brady Wagoner, 241-259. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2026

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009393133.012>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Working Paper

Hategekimana, Vestin, Anna Marino, Maeva Perrin, Eloise Thompson, Jessica Gale, Mia Gandenberger, Simon Noori, Didier Ruedin, Aldina Camenisch, Lucas Oesch and Robin Stünzi. "Crises, Migration and (Im) Mobility: Towards a Reflexive and Multilevel Approach". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 37: 33, 2024. Collaborative (IP48, IP47, IP45, IP43, IP42 and IP40).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832029>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

III_IP48_LEGACIES

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Blankvoort, Nadine, Iva Dodevska and Stefan Manser-Egli. "The coloniality of integration: Rethinking the science-policy nexus". *Ethnicities*: 14687968261447880, 2026.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/14687968261447880>

Replication data unavailable (Other secondary data)

Blankvoort, Nadine, Iva Dodevska and Stefan Manser-Egli. "The coloniality of integration: Rethinking the science-policy nexus". *Ethnicities*: 14687968261447880, 2026.

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Replication data unavailable (Other secondary data)

Dahinden, Janine. "...when the category 'migration' lost its innocence for migration scholars. And what now? A plea for dialogue". *Comparative Migration Studies*, 13, 37: 1-7, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-025-00459-7>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Klauser, F.. "Aerial legacies of COVID-19". *Geographica Helvetica*, 80, 3: 229–239, 2025.

<https://gh.copernicus.org/articles/80/229/2025/>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Manser-Egli, Stefan and Philipp Lutz. "Integration for whom? The migration bias in social norms". *European Societies*: 1-20, 2025. Collaborative (IP48 and IP39).

<https://doi.org/10.1162/euso.a.30>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Manser-Egli, Stefan. "Illiberal integrationism: shared values as an integration requirement in liberal democracy". *Journal of Political Power*, 19, 1: 83-102, 2026.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/2158379X.2025.2538462>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Manser-Egli, Stefan. "Integration as a totalizing institution: a moral economy of street-level knowledge production on immigrant integration". *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 51, 10: 2547-2565, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2025.2461346>

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Manser-Egli, Stefan. "Respecting the values of the constitution: Integration in the community of value(s)". *Frontiers in Political Science*, 5: 1124552, 2023.

<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpos.2023.1124552>

Replication data unavailable (No SNSF data collection funding)

Piccoli, Lorenzo, Matteo Gianni, Didier Ruedin, Christin Achermann, Janine Dahinden, Paula Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, Mihaela Nedelcu and Tania Zittoun. "What Is the Nexus between Migration and Mobility? A Framework to Understand the Interplay between Different Ideal Types of Human Movement". *Sociology*, 58, 5: 1019-1037, 2024. Collaborative (IP40, IP48, IP47 and IP45).

<https://doi.org/10.1177/00380385241228836>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Schnell, Mathis, Philip Balsiger and Janine Dahinden. "Sexual asylum regimes and politics of belonging: Narratives of deservingness in the political-public discourse in Switzerland". *Migration Studies*, 12, 4: mnae042, 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/migration/mnae042>

Replication data available on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/15861943>

Schnell, Mathis. "Credibility Assessments in Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity Asylum Cases: Evidence from a Quantitative Study of Case Law in Switzerland". *Swiss Journal of Sociology*, 50, 3: 333–360, 2024.

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Dahinden, Janine and Andreas Pott. "Reflexivities and Knowledge Production in Migration Studies: Pitfalls and Alternatives". *Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2025*

<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-03337-6>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Dahinden, Janine. "Migranticization". In *"Elgar Encyclopedia of Global Migration"*, edited by Oso, Laura, Natalia Ribas-Mateos and Melissa Moralli, 358 - 360. *Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2025*

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Replication data unavailable (No SNSF data collection funding)

Duyvendak, Jan Willem and Mathis Schnell. "The culturalization and emotionalization of citizenship". In *"Encyclopedia of Citizenship Studies"*, edited by García Cabeza, Marisol and Thomas Faist, 399-404. *Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2024*

<https://www.elgaronline.com/view/book/9781800880467/ch69.xml>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Working Paper

de Athougua Filipe, Sara, Vestin Hategekimana, Anna Marino, Carol Pierre, Didier Ruedin, Mathis Schnell and Great Udochi. "Do Spatial Political Focus, Feelings of Belonging, and Social Networks Affect the Intention to Apply for Citizenship? Evidence from Switzerland". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series, 38: 28, 2025.*

Collaborative (IP48, IP42, IP41 and IP40).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14710110>

Replication data available on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/7936301>

Hategekimana, Vestin, Anna Marino, Maeva Perrin, Eloise Thompson, Jessica Gale, Mia Gandenberger, Simon Noori, Didier Ruedin, Aldina Camenisch, Lucas Oesch and Robin Stünzi. "Crises, Migration and (Im) Mobility: Towards a Reflexive and Multilevel Approach". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series, 37: 33, 2024.*

Collaborative (IP48, IP47, IP45, IP43, IP42 and IP40).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832029>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Publications Phase III (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Dahinden, Janine. "Deterritorialized and unfinished "integration nations"?". *Ethnic and Racial Studies, 46, 8: 1609-1619, 2023.*

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2022.2130705>

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III_IP49_PRECARIZATION

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Kurt, Stefanie and Livia Tomás. "Migrantische Arbeitskräfte im Schweizer Gastgewerbe". *Jusletter, Zurich: 1-21, 2026.*

https://jusletter.weblaw.ch/juslissues/2026/1281/migrantische-arbeits_978c149114.html_ONCE&login=false

Łysienia, Maja and Stefanie Kurt. "Evolving legal precarity? The case of persons displaced from Ukraine". *Jusletter, 14.4.2025, 2025.*

https://jusletter.weblaw.ch/juslissues/2025/1237/evolving-legal-preca_5ed74bec16.html_ONCE&login=false

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Łysienia, Maja. "Dzieci w strzeżonych ośrodkach dla cudzoziemców – orzecznictwo Europejskiego Trybunału Praw Człowieka a polskie prawo i praktyka". *Dziecko krzywdzone. Teoria badania praktyka, 23, 2: 13-49, 2024.*

<https://dzieckokrzywdzone.fdds.pl/index.php/DK/article/view/923>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Waldis, Barbara and Stefanie Kurt. "It is normal, that is, difficult": Care obligation and solidarity in Balkan-Swiss families during the COVID-19 pandemic". *Transitions: Journal of Transient Migration*, 9, 1: 49-66, 2025.

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Replication data unavailable (No SNSF data collection funding)

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Borrelli, Lisa Marie, Stefanie Kurt and Nora Ratzmann. "Sozialpolitik und Migrationskontrolle. Gemeinsamkeiten und Unterschiede in Deutschland, Österreich und der Schweiz". *Bielefeld: transcript Verlag*, 2026

<https://www.transcript-verlag.de/978-3-8376-8290-8/sozialpolitik-und-migrationskontrolle/?c=313000000>

Piñeiro, Esteban, Stefanie Kurt, Eva Mey and Peter Streckeisen. "Soziale Arbeit und Integrationspolitik in der Schweiz, Professionelle Positionsbestimmungen". *Zurich: Seismo Verlag*, 2023

<https://www.seismoverlag.ch/de/daten/soziale-arbeit-und-integrationspolitik-in-der-schweiz/>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Book Chapters

Kurt, Stefanie. "Art. 4". In *"Ausländer- und Integrationsgesetz (AIG)"*, edited by Caroni, Martina and Daniela Thurnherr, 30-41. *Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag*, 2024

<https://staempflierecht.ch/auslaender-und-integrationsgesetz-aig/ean-9783727243134>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Kurt, Stefanie. "Art. 53". In *"Ausländer- und Integrationsgesetz (AIG)"*, edited by Caroni, Martina and Daniela Thurnherr, 667-676. *Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag*, 2024

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Kurt, Stefanie. "Art. 53a". In *"Ausländer- und Integrationsgesetz (AIG)"*, edited by Caroni, Martina and Daniela Thurnherr, 677-679. *Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag*, 2024

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Kurt, Stefanie. "Art. 55". In *"Ausländer- und Integrationsgesetz (AIG)"*, edited by Caroni, Martina and Daniela Thurnherr, 683-685. *Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag*, 2024

<https://staempflierecht.ch/auslaender-und-integrationsgesetz-aig/ean-9783727243134>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Kurt, Stefanie. "Art. 55a". In *"Ausländer- und Integrationsgesetz (AIG)"*, edited by Caroni, Martina and Daniela Thurnherr, 686-687. *Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag*, 2024

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Kurt, Stefanie. "Art. 56". In *"Ausländer- und Integrationsgesetz (AIG)"*, edited by Caroni, Martina and Daniela Thurnherr, 688-694. *Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag*, 2024

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Kurt, Stefanie. "Integration im Migrationsrecht - eine Übersicht". In *"Soziale Arbeit und Integrationspolitik in der Schweiz, Professionelle Positionsbestimmungen"*, edited by Piñeiro, Esteban, Stefanie Kurt, Eva Mey and Peter Streckeisen, 41-54. Zurich: Seismo Verlag, 2023

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

Mey, Eva. "Das institutionelle Arrangement der Integrationspolitik in der Schweiz". In *"Soziale Arbeit und Integrationspolitik in der Schweiz, Professionelle Positionsbestimmungen"*, edited by Piñeiro, Esteban, Stefanie Kurt, Eva Mey and Peter Streckeisen, 55-69. Zurich: Seismo Verlag, 2023

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

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Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

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Gago, Angie. "The 'migranticisation' of EU free movement: Analysing the policies to control intra-EU migration in Germany and the UK". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 34: 21, 2023.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10952564>

Replication data available on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/7605100>

Łysienia, Maja. "Crisis-Induced Changes in Migration Laws and Policies: Investigating the Impact of Crises on Migrant Workers and Forced Migrants in Poland". *nccr – on the move Working Paper Series*, 39: 45, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16778962>

Replication data unavailable (No data collected)

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Publications Phase III (Minor Contribution from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Bornemann, Jonas and Francesco Maiani. "Temporal Governance, Precarity in the New Pact on Migration and Asylum". *European Public Law*, 31, 3: 371-392, 2025.

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III_NCCR

Publications Phase III (Resulting directly from the NCCR)

Journal Articles

Piguet, Etienne and Andreas Perret. "Data visualization tool for a fairer geography of refugee protection in Europe". *Data & Policy*, 7: e63, 2025. Collaborative (NCCR and IP-NCCR).

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